

Backstepping Design and Fractional Differential Equation of Chaotic System

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Abstract : In this paper, backstepping method is proposed to synchronize two fractional-order systems. The simulation results show that this method can effectively synchronize two chaotic systems.

Keywords : backstepping method, fractional order, synchronization, chaotic system

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